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Supplementary Material for **Building Earth with pebbles made of chondritic components**

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Supplementary Text

Fig. S1

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References

Figure S1: Pebble streamlines for different Stokes numbers (St). The pebbles following the blue (red) curves are captured (escape from) by the protoplanet in its orbital plane. Arrows on the streamlines indicate the direction of pebble motion relative to the motion of the protoplanet. Ω and r_{Hill} stand for the orbital frequency and Hill radius of the protoplanet.

1 DETAILS OF THE INVERSION TECHNIQS

2 1. Least-Squares (LS) inversion

3 For both LS and MC, C_{ji} is expressed as a $j \times i$ matrix whereas E_j and U_{E_j} are column matrices
4 with dimensions of $j \times 1$. Prior to using C_{ji} as inputs of inversion methods, we normalized its
5 i^{th} column to the sum of E_j to preserve mass balance in equation (17).

6 We have applied both weights and constraints to the inversion problem in equation (17).
7 For the first part, the aim is to create C'_{ji} , and E'_j from C_{ji} , and E_j . First, we have created a
8 weight matrix representing the $\frac{1}{U_{E_j}}$. Now, when we perform a dot product between the weight
9 matrix and each column of C_{ji} , we get C'_{ji} . Similarly, we find E'_j is a dot product of the weight
10 matrix and E_j . Now using these new matrices as inputs, we find X_i using the ‘Scipy’ optimizer
11 in Python. As negative values of X_i do not have physical meaning, we put constrains on X_i to
12 vary between 0 and 1 to obtain only non-negative values. The final solution is X_i normalized
13 by its sum.

14 2. Markov-Chain Monte Carlo (MC) inversion

15 Following the Bayesian theorem, we find the probability (posterior) of X_i by using a slice
16 sampling algorithm. The likelihood of this model is given by the negative value of the rms
17 misfit as defined in equation (18). The prior is the bound or constraint on X_i for a non-negative
18 solution, that is, $0 < X_i < 1$. Starting from X_i found by LS, the slice sampling technique generates
19 random posteriors by moving between uniformly spaced points. By iterating several tens of
20 thousands of times, the entire posterior space is covered. The final X_i is the maximum posterior
21 normalized by its sum.

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23 Table S1: Input concentrations used for the Chondrite model and the Earth, in mg/g.

Element	IM ^a	C Chon ^b	EL Chon ^b	EH Chon ^b	O Chon ^b	Earth ^c	Earth uncertainty ^c
Fe	910	218.75	290	220	225	312	10
Ni	80	12.525	17.5	13	12.733333	17.7	0.8
Si	2	137.25	167	186	181	160	8
Mg	0	126	106	141	147.333333	151	2
Ca	0	14.175	8.5	10.1	12.866667	16.7	1
Al	0	13.05	8.1	10.5	11.8	15.4	0.9
O	0	408	280	310	378	308	7
Ti	0.005	0.69	0.45	0.58	0.616667	0.792	0.052
Cr	0.02	3.2125	3.15	3.05	3.76	3.883	0.583
Li	0	0.0013425	0.0021	0.00058	0.001867	0.00159	0.00024
Mn	10	1.675	2.2	1.63	2.503333	1.76	0.89
Na	0	4.1	6.8	5.8	6.8	2.201	0.188
K	0	0.40375	0.8	0.735	0.798333	0.227	0.03
Zn	0.001	0.17825	0.25	0.017	0.047667	0.0459	0.004
P	2	0.9875	2	1.17	0.96	0.957	0.3
S	7	33.5	58	33	21.666667	6.096	1.463
Au	0.001	0.00015925	0.00033	0.000225	0.000172	0.000157	0.000059
As	0.005	0.0017975	0.00345	0.0022	0.00165	0.00163	0.0006
Cu	0.15	0.11525	0.185	0.11	0.084	0.069	0.0192
Ag	0.00003	0.00014225	0.000236	0.000023	0.000061	0.0000813	0.0000294
Sb	0.00005	0.0001145	0.000196	0.00009	0.000066	0.0000468	0.0000163
Ga	0.05	0.007675	0.016	0.011	0.005567	0.00449	0.00061
Ge	0.15	0.0235	0.042	0.028	0.010667	0.00856	0.00295
Te	0	0.0015575	0.00223	0.0008	0.00041	0.000334	0.000124
Sn	0	0.00113	0.0008	0	0.000523	0.000239	0.000062
Se	0	0.01205	0.0255	0.0135	0.008867	0.00286	0.00106
Co	5	0.6065	0.84	0.67	0.63	0.841	0.046
Ru	0.005	0.00095325	0.000915	0.000831	0.000617	0.001284	0.000485
Mo	0.006	0.001605	0	0	0.001367	0.00164	0.00061
Re	0.0001	0.00005075	0.000052	0.000047	0.000048	0.0000698	0.0000264
Os	0.001	0.00068625	0.000654	0.000589	0.000578	0.000886	0.000335
Ir	0.002	0.0006375	0.000565	0.000525	0.000537	0.000851	0.000321
Pt	0.01	0.001135	0.0012	0	0.0011	0.001775	0.000671
W	0.001	0.0001475	0	0	0.00009	0.000171	0.000062
Rh	0.001	0.000096	0	0	0.000073	0.000223	0.000084

24 IM= Iron Meteorite; Chon = Chondrite.

25 Sources: a Scott (2020); b Wasson and Kallemeyn (1988); c Wang et al. (2018).

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29 Table S2: Input concentrations used for the Component model (CMA), in mg/g.

Element	MG [#]	C Ch ^h	E Ch ⁱ	O Ch ⁱ	CAI ^h	AOA ^h
Fe	950	269.58	270.9	227.87	0	61.02
Ni	50	15.55	16.1	12.97	0	3.23
Si	0	180.27	185.7	193.57	118	209.3
Mg	0	159.23	124.8	153.97	60.47	286.72
Ca	0	14.79	9.88	13.4	193.55	0
Al	0	14	9.3	12.47	183.26	0
O	0	332.46	320.25	352.67	432.64	436.65
Ti	0	0.75	0.51	0.66	9.85	0
Cr	0	4.07	3.28	4.023	0.41	2.21
Li	0	0.00081	0.0014	0.001916667	0	0.00732
Mn	0	1.48	2.08	2.59	0.1	0.71
Na	0	2.88	6.615	7.21	0	0
K	0	0.21	0.805	0.84	0	0
Zn	0	0.0368	0.225	0	0	0
P	0	1.14	1.52	0.96	0	0
S	0	2.57	45.05	16.03333333	0	0
Au	0	0.00017617	0.0003185	0.000188667	0	0
As	0	0.0017	0.00329	0.00163	0	0
Cu	0	0.09189	0.2055	0.074066667	0	0
Ag	0	0.00005	0.00015415	0.0000319	0	0
Sb	0	0.00006155	0.00016375	4.76E-05	0	0
Ga	0	0.0043	0.01395	0.004753333	0	0
Ge	0	0.01047	0.0372	0.006643333	0	0
Te	0	0.00029	0.00157	0.000173333	0	0
Sn	0	0.00024	0.00043	0.000563333	0	0
Se	0	0.00154	0.0229	0.006636667	0	0
Co	0	0.72	0.78	0.646666667	0	0.16
Ru	0	0.00111432	0.000827	0.000867667	0.00272067	0
Mo	0	0.00111432	0.0011415	0.001201	0.00409365	0
Re	0	0.00006174	0.0000505	5.03E-05	0.000264	0
Os	0	0.00079475	0.000578	0.000611	0.003125	0
Ir	0	0.00079307	0.0005495	0.000558333	0.002131	0
Pt	0	0.00155771	0.001199	0.001189333	0.00491147	0
W	0	0.00017066	0.000149	0.000140333	0.00182977	0
Rh	0	0.00015364	0.000174	0.000173667	0.00158219	0

30 MG = Metal grain; Ch = Chondrule.

31 Sources: h Alexander (2022); i Alexander (2019); # Assumed pure Fe-Ni metal grains.

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Elemental compositions of chondritic components

38 We have collected the in-situ elemental concentrations of chondritic components: metal grains,
39 chondrules, calcium-aluminum-rich-inclusions (CAIs), and amoeboid-olivine-aggregates (AOAs) from
40 relevant published values. The details of data collection are described below. Table 3 summarizes the
41 elemental abundances of individual components.

42 **Metal grains:** Three types of metal grains are found in most chondrites: individual grains embedded in
43 the matrix material, metal grains within the chondrules, and metallic rims around the chondrules. For
44 this study, we are interested in individual grains in the matrix. Since we use bulk compositions of
45 chondrules, the second type of grains are associated with chondrules. Metal rims are not part of the
46 chondrules.

47 The metal grains in a chondrite contain mostly Fe and Ni. However, they possess variable
48 proportions of other metals (Co, Cr), Si, some fractions of siderophile (Sn, Au, Cu, Ru, Mo, Re, Os, Ir,
49 Pt, W, Rh) and volatile elements (Zn, Mn, P, S). We used mean compositions of individual metal grains
50 in CR, CV, CM (Van Kooten et al., 2022), EH (Kadlag et al., 2019), EL (from a PhD thesis by Van
51 Niekerk, 2012) and median composition of L/LL (Okabayashi et al., 2019) chondrites. Then we
52 computed an average of them for this study. We assumed that the concentrations of the rest of the
53 elements are zero because they are either found in negligible amounts or not found in the metal grains.

54 **Chondrules:** Chondrules are mostly molten droplets of silicates. However, they contain volatile and
55 siderophile elements as well. Elemental concentrations in the bulk chondrules are collected for different
56 carbonaceous (CO, CR, CV, CM, CH, CB, CK) and enstatite (EH and EL), and ordinary (H, L, and L)
57 chondrites from a published database (Hezel et al., 2018). The database assembles the chondrules
58 composition measured by mostly two techniques: mechanical separation and freeze-thaw method. In
59 the former case, the chondrules are separated from the chondrite mechanically. In the latter case, the
60 chondrite fragments are poured into the liquid nitrogen and boiling water repetitively until their
61 components are separated. Therefore, chondrules collected by both methods represent roughly a bulk
62 chondrule composition. We computed averages over subgroups of carbonaceous and non-carbonaceous
63 chondrule and used C, E, and O chondrule compositions.

64 **Calcium-aluminum-rich-inclusions (CAIs) and amoeboid-olivine-aggregates (AOAs):** The major
65 element composition of refractory inclusions is often measured in terms of their primary and secondary
66 mineral contents. However, the former can be computed from known mineral concentrations, the
67 relative abundance of the constituent minerals, and the molecular weights of the elements. We have
68 collected mineral concentrations in multiple Allende CAI samples from a thesis work by Roberta, 1976.
69 Then we computed their average compositions. Finally, the averaged major and minor element
70 concentrations (Fe, Si, Ca, Al, Mg, O, Na, Ti) were found. Concentrations of Cr, Mn, Co, Ni, Zn, Au,
71 and W were averaged over the multiple samples reported in the same source. We collected the measured
72 concentrations of refractory siderophile elements (Ru, Re, Os, Ir, Pt) in Allend CAIs from Archer et al.
73 (2014) and computed their average.

74 The median mineral concentrations in bulk AOAs in CV3 chondrites are taken from Ruzicka
75 et al. (2012). We chose the data measured by the DB-EMP method because it is most suitable for

76 measuring bulk concentrations (please follow the mentioned reference for details). Then the major +
 77 minor element (Fe, Ni, Si, Mg, Ca, Al, O, S, Cr, Na, Mn) compositions were calculated. Concentrations
 78 of some volatile and refractory siderophile elements (Au, As, Sb, Ru, Ir) are taken from Grossman et
 79 al. (1979). We have computed an average of the concentrations of those elements over all of their
 80 samples except 4, 6, and 7 which are recognized as exceptional samples in the respective paper.

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82 Table S3: Input concentrations used for the Component model (CDB), in mg/g.

Element	MG ^{a,b,c}	C Ch ^d	E Ch ^d	O Ch ^d	CAI ^e	AOA ^{f,g}	Matrix ^d
Fe	908	115.714	27.35	99.90941	40.32	60.894	262.57
Ni	61.53	6.9567	1.021	3.46363	0.19	2.6	12.24
Si	6.70192	206.2467	259.97	232.47024	102.849	180.112	139.14
Mg	0.09375	210.6749	206.66224	171.9693	40.857	226.936	103.85
Ca	0.28945	20.8244	10.11	18.04946	95.426	32.944	12.7
Al	0	20.4976	11.45	17.31855	202.416	38.853	15.15
O	0	385.1024	458.965	437.571	388.872	415.19	475.97
Ti	0	1.3698	0.48007	1.3269	2.537	0.41452	0.561
Cr	1.4172	3.8527	2.49	3.81013	0.6044	1.664	2.57
Li	0	0.0017	0.00195	0.00073	0	0	0.004
Mn	0.04924	1.449	1.57973	3.14383	0.28925	0.879	1.955
Na	0	4.0186	6.56191	9.94698	38.577	0.2529	4.416
K	0	0.4612	0.95853	1.55115	1.828	0.09642	1.194
Zn	0.00028	0.0614	0.08468	0.05664	0.932	0	0.1868
P	1.51325	0.6761	0.20924	0.37346	0	0.12021	1.018
S	0.26519	6.5774	18.17143	5.9906	0	1.267	17.16
Au	0.0009	0.00011	0.000017	0.000077	0.0000336	0.00019029	0.000174
As	0.00354	0.002051	0.00034	0.001064	0	0.00304	0.00171
Cu	0.08012	0.1047	0.29388	0.05242	0	0	0.327
Ag	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sb	0.00012	0	0.00002	0	0	0.000212	0
Ga	0.02316	0.002324	0.00234	0.003124	0	0	0.0172
Ge	0.06493	0	0	0.014015	0	0	0
Te	0	0	0.00054	0	0	0	0
Sn	0.00063	0	0	0	0	0	0
Se	0	0.008394	0.01209	0.01033	0	0	0.0116
Co	4.53593	0.4405	0.04916	0.21658	0.02296	0.10234	0.7566
Ru	0.00318	0	0.00026	0	0.0081877	0.00233	0
Mo	0.00326	0.00227	0.00041	0.002336	0	0	0
Re	0.00017	0.000164	0	0	0.000503035	0	0
Os	0.00216	0.000961	0.000101	0	0.0053028	0	0.0005
Ir	0.00186	0.000801	0.00005	0.00053	0.0067618	0.00154	0.000401
Pt	0.00411	0	0	0	0.0133053	0	0
W	0.00054	0.000243	0.000071	0.000381	0.002175	0	0.000185
Rh	0.00076	0	0	0	0	0	0

83 MG = Metal grain; Ch = Chondrule.

84 Sources: a Van Kooten et al. (2022); b Kadlag et al. (2019); c Okabayashi et al. (2019); d Hezel et al.
 85 (2018); e Archer et al. (2014); f Ruzicka et al. (2012); g Grossman et al. (1979).

86 Table S4: Input isotope concentrations used for the Chondrite and Component (CDB, CMA) models
 87 and the bulk Earth.

Chondrite model						
Element	CM Chon ^k	CV Chon ^k	EL Chon ^k	EH Chon ^k	L Chon ^k	
$\delta^{17}\text{O}$	1.2	-2.25	3	2.7	4.9	
$\delta^{18}\text{O}$	7.5	2.2	5.7	5.4	3.5	
Element	C Chon ^p		EL Chon ^p	EH Chon ^p	O Chon ^p	
$\varepsilon^{54}\text{Cr}$	1		0.01	-0.01	-0.35	
$\varepsilon^{50}\text{Ti}$	3		0.1	-0.01	-0.5	

CMA model						
Element	C Ch ^h	E Ch ⁱ	O Ch ⁱ	CAI ^h	AOA ^h	Matrix
$\Delta^{17}\text{O}$	-3.8 ^q	-0.01	0.08	-20.06	-20.06	-
$\delta^{18}\text{O}$	-2.36 ^q	5.23	4.13	-37.18	-37.18	-
$\varepsilon^{54}\text{Cr}$	-0.75	0.08	-0.34	8	8	-
$\varepsilon^{50}\text{Ti}$	-4.25	-0.2	-0.69	8.11	8.11	-

CDB model							
Element	C Ch	E Ch	O Ch	CAI	AOA	Matrix	Earth
$\delta^{17}\text{O}$	-2 ^o	2.51 ^o	3.55 ^o	-40.2 ^j	-35.55 ^j	4.07 ^d	2.7 ^k
$\delta^{18}\text{O}$	2 ^o	5.01 ^o	4.68 ^o	-30 ^j	-33.94 ^j	7.08 ^d	5.5 ^k
$\varepsilon^{54}\text{Cr}$	-0.23 ^l	0.12 ^l	-0.123 ^l	6 ⁿ	5 ⁿ	1.06 ^m	0.08 ^p
$\varepsilon^{50}\text{Ti}$	-0.15 ^m	-0.52 ^m	-0.55 ^m	9 ^l	9 ^l	2.28 ^m	0 ^p

88 IM= Iron Meteorite; Chon = Chondrite; MG = Metal grain; Ch = Chondrule.

89 Sources: d Hezel et al. (2018); h Alexander (2022); i Alexander (2019a); j Fagan et al. (2004); k Lodders
 90 (2000); l Williams et al. (2020); m Schneider et al. (2020); n Torrano et al. (2024); o Clayton and
 91 Mayeda (1999); p Warren (2011); q Alexander (2019b)

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